

NITRATION OF SOME COUMARIN DERIVATIVES

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7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin, its methyl ether, 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid and its methyl ester have been nitrated and their nitro derivatives obtained.

Pechmann and Obermiller (*Ber.*, 1901, **34**, 666) claimed to have obtained 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-8-nitrocoumarin by nitrating 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin at 0° but the nitro product obtained in this work had a considerable lowering in melting point with an authentic specimen, prepared according to Chakravarti and Ghosh (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 622). They also claim to have obtained dinitro compound but all attempts to prepare the same proved unsuccessful. No literature is available on the nitration of 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid and its methyl ester.

7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin on nitration under one set of conditions gives a nitro derivative melting at 253°, identical with 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-6-nitrocoumarin, prepared by Chakravarti and Banerji (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **14**, 37) and a trinitro derivative under different conditions, whereas the nitration of its methyl ether under similar conditions gives the nitro derivatives of the methyl ether.

Nitration of 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid gives dinitro and trinitro derivatives, whereas the methyl ester of the same under different conditions gives mono-nitro and dinitro derivatives only. The constitution of these compounds has been established.

EXPERIMENTAL

7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-6-nitrocoumarin.—A mixture of nitric acid (*d* 1.42, 2 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (6 c.c.) was added drop by drop to the well stirred and ice-cooled sulphuric acid solution (40 c.c.) of 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (5 g.). After the addition was complete, the reaction mixture was kept at 5-10° for about 30 minutes and then poured over crushed ice, when yellow flakes separated. The crude product after crystallisation from acetic acid melted at 253°. (Found: N, 6.5. $C_{10}H_7O_5N$ requires N, 6.3 per cent). Mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen showed no lowering.

7-Methoxy-4-methyl-6-nitrocoumarin.—7-Methoxy-4-methylcoumarin (1 g.), suspended in acetic acid (20 c.c.) was treated with nitric acid (*d* 1.42, 4 c.c.) and the reaction mixture was kept on a boiling water-bath for about 30 minutes. When cold, the solution gave some yellow needles, m.p. 282°. The mother-liquor gave more solid on dilution. (Found: N, 6.1. $C_{11}H_9O_5N$ requires N, 5.95 per cent).

The same compound was obtained by methylating the above hydroxy-nitrocoumarin in dry acetone solution with methyl iodide in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate and by boiling for 20 hours. The solid obtained after removal of the liquids was first washed with 2% solution of caustic soda and then crystallised from acetic acid.

This nitro derivative was heated with anhydrous aluminium chloride at 150°-160° for about 3 hours and then the mixture was treated with dilute hydrochloric acid and filtered. The solid was extracted with a 4% solution of sodium hydroxide and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 253°. It was found identical with 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-6-nitrocoumarin (mixed m.p.).

7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-3:6:8-trinitrocoumarin.—7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (5 g.) was suspended in acetic acid (50 c.c.) and nitric acid (*d* 1.42, 20 c.c.) was gradually added to it. The reaction mixture was heated on a boiling water-bath for about 15 minutes. On cooling, yellow cubes separated, m.p. 225-26° (decomp.). (Found: N, 13.8. $C_{10}H_5O_9N_3$ requires N, 13.5 per cent).

The same substance was also obtained by allowing the above mixture to remain at room temperature for about 24 hours.

2:4-Dihydroxy-3:5-dinitroacetophenone.—The above trinitrocoumarin (1 g.) was heated with liquor ammonia on a boiling water-bath for about 2 hours. The orange solution¹⁷ was acidified after cooling, filtered, and the filtrate extracted with ether. The solid obtained after removal of the ether was crystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 168-69°. (Found: N, 11.7. $C_8H_6O_7N_2$ requires N, 11.6 per cent). Mixed melting point with an authentic specimen of 2:4-dihydroxy-3:5-dinitroacetophenone showed no lowering.

7-Methoxy-4-methyl-3:6:8-trinitrocoumarin.—7-Methoxy-4-methylcoumarin (1 g.) was nitrated in sulphuric acid solution (10 c.c.) by using a mixture of nitric acid (4 c.c., *d* 1.42) and sulphuric acid (4 c.c.) at 5-10° for about half an hour, when a small quantity of a crystalline substance separated. More solid was obtained when the mixture was poured over crushed ice. It crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles, m.p. 180-81°. (Found: N, 13.1. $C_{11}H_7O_9N_3$ requires N, 12.9 per cent).

Demethylation with 30% solution of hydrobromic acid in acetic acid, by heating at 140-50° for about 2 hours, gave the corresponding hydroxy compound.

Methyl 7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-8-nitrocoumarin-6-carboxylate.—Methyl 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (5 g.) was suspended in acetic acid (75 c.c.) and nitric acid (*d* 1.42, 40 c.c.) was added to it dropwise, when the ester gradually went into solution and after some time crystals began to separate. After 3 hours the flask was cooled in ice for some time and the solid filtered. It crystallised from acetic acid in pale yellow needles, m.p. 256-57°. Some more substance was obtained from the mother-liquor on dilution. (Found: N, 5.2. $C_{12}H_9O_7N$ requires N, 5.02 per cent).

Hydrolysis.—(a). The above substance was hydrolysed by boiling with 20% sodium hydroxide solution (40 c.c.) for about 4 hours, acidified with hydrochloric acid and then steam-distilled, when the nitro compound was obtained which crystallised from alcohol in orange needles, m.p. 85° (mixed m.p. with 2-nitroresorcinol).

(b). When it was hydrolysed with 20% sodium hydroxide (40 c.c. for 1 g.) at room temperature for about 3 days, it gave 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-8-nitrocoumarin-6-carboxylic acid, which crystallised from acetic acid in pale yellow needles, m.p. 288° (decomp.). It gave a violet colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. It is sparingly soluble in alcohol, acetic acid and insoluble in benzene, carbon tetrachloride and water. (Found: N, 5.5. $C_{11}H_7O_7N$ requires N, 5.3 per cent).

Hydrolysis with sulphuric acid (5 c.c.) in glacial acetic acid (40 c.c. for 1 g.) by boiling for 3 hours gave the same acid. The acid was esterified to the original ester by boiling with methyl alcohol in presence of sulphuric acid for 16 hours.

Methyl 7-Methoxy-4-methyl-8-nitrocoumarin-6-carboxylate.—Sodium salt of methyl 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-8-nitrocoumarin-6-carboxylate was prepared by dissolving it in absolute alcohol and then adding 25% solution of sodium hydroxide, when the salt separated. It was filtered, washed with absolute alcohol and dried at 160°.

The dry salt (1 g.) was suspended in dry toluene (30 c.c.), dimethyl sulphate (1.5 c.c.) added and the mixture refluxed at 120° for 6 hours. Toluene was removed by steam-distillation and the residue was washed with dilute sodium hydroxide solution and then with water. It crystallised from methyl alcohol in pale yellow needles, m.p. 189-90°. It is soluble in methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, acetic acid and benzene. (Found: N, 4.5. C₁₃H₁₁O₇N requires N, 4.8 per cent).

Methyl 7-Acetoxy-4-methyl-8-nitrocoumarin-6-carboxylate.—The hydroxy compound (1 g.) was heated at 140°-145° with acetic anhydride (7 c.c.) and pyridine (2-3 drops) for about 4 hours. It was then diluted with ice-cold water when a pasty mass was obtained which slowly solidified on standing at room temperature. It crystallised from acetic acid in shining white needles, m.p. 222-23°. (Found: N, 4.5. C₁₄H₁₁O₈N requires N, 4.4 per cent).

Methyl 7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-3:8-dinitrocoumarin-6-carboxylate—(a). Nitric acid (d 1.42, 20 c.c.) was gradually added to methyl 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (5 g.), suspended in acetic acid (50 c.c.) and the mixture heated on a boiling water-bath for about an hour. Some yellow cubes separated on cooling the reaction mixture, which melted at 246-47° (decomp.). Dilution of the mother-liquor with water gave a further amount of the compound. It gave a reddish coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride. It is sparingly soluble in methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol and acetic acid. (Found: N, 8.7. C₁₂H₉O₇N₂ requires N, 8.6 per cent).

(b). It was also obtained when nitration of the ester (1 g.) in acetic acid (15 c.c.) with nitric acid (d 1.42, 8 c.c.) was allowed to proceed at room temperature for 3 days. (After 3 hours the mono-nitro compound first separated which slowly went into solution and finally the required substance separated).

(c). A mixture of nitric acid (4 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (4 c.c.) was added to the ester (1 g.), dissolved in sulphuric acid (8 c.c.) and surrounded by ice. The reaction mixture was left at room temperature for about 30 minutes and then poured over crushed ice, when the dinitro compound was obtained.

Methyl 7-Acetoxy-4-methyl-3:8-dinitrocoumarin-6-carboxylate.—The above dinitro ester was acetylated with acetic anhydride in presence of pyridine yielding pale yellow cubes, m.p. 198-99°. (Found: N, 7.8. C₁₄H₁₀O₁₀N₂ requires N, 7.7 per cent).

2:4-Dihydroxy-3-nitro-5-carbomethoxyacetophenone.—Methyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-3:8-dinitrocoumarin-6-carboxylate (5 g.) was boiled with liquor ammonia (200 c.c.) until all ammonia was driven out. When cold, the reaction mixture was acidified and the precipitate obtained was repeatedly crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 194-95°. It gave a red coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: N, 5.8. C₁₀H₇O₇N requires N, 5.5 per cent).

2:4-Dihydroxy-3-nitro-5-carboxy-acetophenone.—The above compound was hydrolysed by heating on a boiling water-bath with 8% sodium hydroxide (20 c.c.) for about an hour. It crystallised from water, acidified with a few drops of hydrochloric acid, in tiny needles, m.p. 242-43°. It is very soluble in methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, acetic acid and sparingly soluble in benzene and chloroform. (Found: N, 5.9. $C_9H_7O_7N$ requires N, 5.8 per cent). The phenylhydrazone was obtained in yellow needles from acetic acid, m.p. 258-59°. (Found N, 12.3. $C_{15}H_{13}O_6N_2$ requires N, 12.2 per cent).

2:4-Dihydroxy-3-nitro-acetophenone.—The above compound was heated in a sealed tube at 140-145° for about 10 hours with water (7 c.c.), acetic acid (5 c.c.) and hydrochloric acid (5 c.c.). The reaction mixture was then extracted with ether. The residue after removal of the ether was left in an alkaline desiccator and the solid finally crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 93°. (Found: N, 7.3. $C_8H_7O_5N$ requires N, 7.1 per cent). (Mixed m.p. with a genuine specimen).

7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-3:8-dinitrocoumarin-6-carboxylic Acid.—Sulphuric acid (5 c.c.) was added to the solution of methyl 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-3:8-dinitrocoumarin-6-carboxylate (1 g.) in acetic acid (20 c.c.) and boiled for 3 hours. Yellow needles separated on cooling the solution. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 275-76° (decomp.). (Found: N, 8.9. $C_{11}H_9O_8N_2$ requires N, 9.03 per cent).

It was esterified to the original ester by boiling it with methyl alcohol in presence of sulphuric acid for 16 hours.

7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-6:8-dinitrocoumarin.—Fuming nitric acid (d 1.5, 30 c.c.) was gradually added to 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid (5 g.), suspended in acetic acid (75 c.c.) when a considerable rise in temperature took place. After 15 minutes, small crystals began to separate. The mixture was cooled in ice and the solid filtered, washed with water and crystallised from acetic acid in yellow cubes, m.p. 291-92° (decomp.). It is sparingly soluble in acetic acid, insoluble in benzene, chloroform and carbon tetrachloride. (Found: N, 10.6. $C_{10}H_8O_7N_2$ requires N, 10.7 per cent).

7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-3:6:8-trinitrocoumarin.—7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid (1 g.), suspended in acetic acid (10 c.c.) was treated with fuming nitric acid (8 c.c.) as above, but the reaction was allowed to proceed for 4 days, when crystals first formed redissolved and new crystals were formed. It crystallised from acetic acid in yellow cubes, m. p. 225-26°. (Found: N, 13.7. $C_{10}H_5O_9N_3$ requires N, 13.5 per cent).

The substance was also obtained by nitrating 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-3:8-dinitro-6-carboxylic acid with fuming nitric acid in acetic acid solution for about 4 days as well as from 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin.